

Hot Amperometric Titration for Estimation of Trace Amounts of Lanthanum and Cerium

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Trace amounts of La^{III} and Ce^{III} have been estimated quantitatively with xylenol orange (XO) using hot amperometric titration technique. In hot condition, the increase in reversibility and ease of reduction facilitate the metal-ligand complexation. The titrations have been performed at $\text{pH } 5.5$, $\mu=0.2$ and $\text{temp.}=70^\circ$. The stoichiometric ratio of metal-XO complex is found to be 1 : 1. Many ions do not interfere the titration procedure.

In continuation to our work¹⁻³ on the estimation of trace quantity of rare earths by electrometric technique, the present paper reports the use of xylenol orange (XO) as amperometric reagent for the estimation of La^{III} and Ce^{III} . Xylenol orange has been extensively used as complexometric and spectrophotometric reagent⁴⁻⁸. The titrations have been performed in hot experimental set-up, as the results were not reproducible at room temperature.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. La^{III} and Ce^{III} solutions were prepared and standardised⁹. A fresh solution of XO was prepared whenever used. Britton-Robinson buffer was prepared by the known method⁹. Amperometric titrations were done on a manually operated polarograph. Titrations were performed in a thermostatic bath at $70 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Polarography of XO: XO gave two-stage reduction in the pH range 4.6-11.0. Polarograms of different concentrations of XO in Britton-Robinson buffer at $\text{pH } 5.5$, $\text{temp.}=70 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and $\mu=0.2$ were taken. The diffusion current was found to be proportional to the concentration of XO. A slight positive shift in half-wave potential was observed, which might be due to easier reduction and increased degree of reversibility of the electrode process.

Procedure of amperometric titration: Sets of solutions containing known amounts of La^{III} and Ce^{III} at $\mu=0.2$ in appropriate quantity of Britton-Robinson buffer of $\text{pH } 5.5$ were prepared. The plateau potential on the wave of XO, i.e. -1.25 V vs S.C.E. was applied at which La^{III} and Ce^{III} were not electroactive. For titration, titre was taken in a thermostatic bath at $70 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and titrant (XO) was added dropwise and current was noted.

Current-volume plots were reversed L shaped (Fig. 1). The end-point indicated metal-XO complexation ratio of 1 : 1.

Fig. 1. Amperometric titration curves of La^{III} and Ce^{III} with xylenol orange: (A) $0.005 \text{ mM } \text{La}^{\text{III}}$ vs 0.005 M XO , and (B) $0.0125 \text{ mM } \text{Ce}^{\text{III}}$ vs 0.01 M XO .

Results and Discussion

The results of the estimation of La^{III} and Ce^{III} are tabulated (Table 1). Ce^{III} and La^{III} were determined in the concentration range $0.5\text{-}7.0 \mu\text{M}$ with an error less than $\pm 0.80\%$. The statistical data support the precision, confidence and utility of the procedure.

Effect of diverse ions: For interference studies, known amount of foreign ion was added to the definite amount of metal ion solution and the solutions were amperometrically titrated following the procedure as described above. Titrations of 1-2 mg of La^{III} and Ce^{III} were not in any way hampered by the presence of large excess (mg) of the ions, viz. K (146), Na (115), Ca^{II} (75), Mg^{II} (73), Ba^{II} (46), Pb^{II} (39), Tl^{I} (20) and Ag^{I} (11). However, it is

TABLE I—AMPEROMETRIC ESTIMATION OF La^{III} AND Ce^{III} WITH XO AT -1.25 V vs S.C.E.pH=5.5, $\mu=0.2$ (KCl), temp. = $70 \pm 5^\circ$

Concn. of La ^{III} or Ce ^{III} μM	% Error	
	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}
0.5	-0.40	-0.95
1.0	-0.63	+0.37
1.5	+0.58	+0.24
2.0	-0.46	-0.20
2.5	+0.68	+0.47
3.0	+0.75	-0.52
4.0	-0.77	+0.44
5.0	+0.41	-0.35
6.0	-0.80	+0.28
7.0	+0.26	-0.80

Standard deviation for La^{III} = ± 0.18 , and Ce^{III} = ± 0.10 .

observed that Ti^{IV}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Fe^{II} ions interfered seriously.

Conclusion : Amperometric method described above can be considered as a good analytical tool for the estimation of trace amount La^{III} and Ce^{III} using XO as titrant. The conditions under which the estimations made are of practical significance.

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